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NAVIGATING THE STEM LANDSCAPE: SOCIOCULTURAL INFLUENCES ON WOMEN'S STEM PARTICIPATION IN INDIA

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“The more clearly we can focus our attention on the wonders and realities of the universe about us, the less taste we shall have for destruction.”

Rachel Carson, Marine biologist, Conservationist, & Author

ABSTRACT

Despite significant progress in education and economic empowerment, women participation in research and innovation (R& I) in India remains disproportionately low, particularly in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. This under representation is deeply rooted in complex socioeconomic and cultural factors that shape women aspirations, opportunities, and experiences in STEM fields. This study aims to explore the multifaceted barriers that hinder women participation in R&I in India, considering the interplay of societal norms, gender stereotypes, educational disparities, and workplace challenges. It will examine how these factors influence women career choices, access to resources, and overall engagement in the R& I landscape. It also explores the role of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in promoting gender equality in higher education institutions (HEIs) and its potential to empower women in STEM fields. The study also highlights the potential of the NEP 2020 to transform the STEM landscape in India by fostering a more inclusive and equitable environment for women. The findings of this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by women in STEM fields in India and inform the development of effective strategies to promote gender equality in R& I.

Keywords: STEM fields, Socioeconomic factors, Cultural factors, Societal norms, Gender stereotypes, Educational disparities, workplace challenges, career choices, access to resources, National Education Policy 2020, Research and Innovation, Higher Education Institutions.

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INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, women have made significant contributions to the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). However, their achievements often go unrecognized, overshadowed by the more celebrated contributions of their male counterparts. This is due in part to the systemic barriers that have historically hindered women's advancement in STEM fields.

Despite these challenges, numerous women have made groundbreaking discoveries and driven critical social and political transformations. Their stories are often overlooked, but they serve as a testament to the ingenuity and resilience of women in STEM.¹ Recognizing the achievements of these women is not only important for honoring their individual contributions but also for inspiring future generations of women to pursue careers in STEM. By amplifying their voices and ensuring that their legacies are not forgotten, we can help create a more equitable and inclusive STEM landscape.

Here are a few examples of historical women in STEM:

Marie Curie: A physicist and chemist who conducted pioneering research on radioactivity, becoming the first woman to win a Nobel Prize, the first person and only woman to win the Nobel Prize twice, and the only person to win the Nobel Prize in two different scientific fields.

Florence Nightingale: An English nurse, statistician, and social reformer who founded modern nursing and was a notable statistician. She is credited with improving sanitary conditions in hospitals, making nursing a respected profession, and establishing a model for nursing education.

Ada Lovelace: An English mathematician and writer who is widely considered to be the first computer programmer.

¹Historical Women in STEM | Headlines & Heroes' (*The Library of Congress* 8 March 2022) <<https://blogs.loc.gov/headlinesandheroes/2022/03/historical-women-in-stem/>> accessed 28 November 2023

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Hypatia: An ancient Greek mathematician, astronomer, and philosopher, who lived in Alexandria, Egypt, during the 5th century AD. She was a renowned teacher and a leading expert in mathematics, astronomy, and philosophy.

Emmy Noether: A German mathematician who made significant contributions to abstract algebra and theoretical physics. She is considered one of the most important mathematicians of the 20th century.

These are just a few examples of the many women who have made significant contributions in the field of STEM throughout history. Their stories serve as a reminder that women have always been, and will continue to be, at the forefront of scientific discovery and innovation.

SOCIOECONOMIC FACTORS INFLUENCING WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN STEM

A study was conducted to explore the experiences of 25 female STEM professionals in regional Australia regarding barriers and enablers to their careers.² Three main types of barriers were identified: gendered workplace, sexism and gender stereotypes, and expectations about women's responsibilities. These barriers included issues such as lack of confidence, isolation, difficulty gaining promotion, harassment, and work-family balance.

Four main types of enablers were also found: aptitude, role models and mentors, supportive workplace, and internal motivations. These enablers included factors such as determined and resilient nature, broad skill base, belief in equal ability, natural STEM aptitude, teachers, mentors, female role models, supportive family environment, and lifelong interest in STEM.

The study found that women's careers in STEM are influenced by both individual and structural factors. Individual enablers, such as having a proactive personality, academic

² Prieto E and others, 'A Study of Factors Affecting Women's Lived Experiences in STEM' (2022), 9, Humanities and Social Sciences Communications <<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-022-01136-1#Sec16>> accessed 29 November 2023

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achievement, and an interest in STEM from an early age, are important for women to succeed in STEM. However, the study also found that these individual enablers are not enough to overcome the societal and workplace challenges that women face in STEM fields.

The majority of the interviewees in the study had a proactive personality, academic achievement, and an interest in STEM from an early age. The authors suggest that these traits are essential for women to succeed in STEM, but also problematic to assume that all women should have them. They argue that it is important to create a more inclusive environment in STEM that does not require women to conform to a certain stereotype in order to be successful.

The study also found that the gendered or bullying environment in STEM workplaces can have a negative impact on women's careers. Additionally, the difficulty of balancing motherhood and full-time STEM work can also contribute to the low retention of women in STEM careers. The authors call for structural changes, such as more flexible work arrangements and childcare support, to address these issues.

The study found that many of the interviewees were uninformed about STEM careers at school and had polarised views on positive discrimination. The authors suggest that schools and universities should do more to challenge the gendered perception of STEM and that affirmative action policies should be implemented with transparency and fairness.

Overall, the study suggests that both individual and structural factors contribute to the underrepresentation of women in STEM careers. More needs to be done to address these factors so that women have the same opportunities as men to succeed in STEM fields.³

GENDER STEREOTYPES AND CULTURAL NORMS AS BARRIERS TO STEM

Gender stereotypes are beliefs or expectations about the characteristics, abilities and

³*Ibid.* Prieto E and others, 'A Study of Factors Affecting Women's Lived Experiences in STEM' (2022), P.7-9.

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preferences of men and women based on their sex⁴. Cultural norms are the shared values, beliefs and practices of a group of people that influence their behavior and attitudes⁵. Both gender stereotypes and cultural norms can affect how girls and women perceive themselves and their potential in STEM, as well as how they are treated by others in STEM education and careers.

Some of the ways that gender stereotypes and cultural norms can act as barriers to STEM are:

- They can reduce girls' and women's interest, confidence and performance in STEM subjects and activities from an early age, by making them feel that they are not good at or do not belong in STEM⁶.
- They can limit girls' and women's exposure and access to STEM opportunities and resources, such as role models, mentors, scholarships, internships and jobs, by creating biases and discrimination in favor of boys and men.
- They can create a hostile and unwelcoming environment for girls and women in STEM classrooms and workplaces, by fostering harassment, isolation, stereotyping and microaggressions.

EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS AND INSTITUTIONAL PRACTICES: THE HIDDEN BARRIERS

Despite significant strides in recent years, women remain underrepresented in STEM fields (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). This underrepresentation is not simply due to individual choices or lack of aptitude, but rather stems from a complex web of hidden barriers embedded within educational systems and institutional practices.

⁴Light A, 'Gender Bias in Science Devalues the Areas in Which Women Work' (*World Economic Forum* 28 January 2022) <<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/01/stem-science-women-gender-stereotypes-bias-equality/>> accessed 12 December 2023

⁵Musso P and others, 'STEM-Gender Stereotypes: Associations with School Empowerment and School Engagement among Italian and Nigerian Adolescents' (2022) 13 *Frontiers in Psychology* <<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.879178/full>> accessed 12 December 2023

⁶Stephanie Mabel Kong and others, 'Reducing Gender Bias in STEM - MIT Science Policy Review' (*MIT Science Policy Review* 8 August 2020) <<https://sciencepolicyreview.org/2020/08/reducing-gender-bias-in-stem/>> accessed 12 December 2023

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Understanding these barriers is crucial for enacting meaningful change and fostering a more equitable and inclusive STEM landscape for all genders.

Key Hidden Barriers are: -

- Gender Stereotypes and Biases: STEM fields are often stereotyped as masculine, discouraging girls and young women from pursuing them. These stereotypes pervade textbooks, classroom interactions, toys, and even extracurricular activities, shaping girls' self-perception and limiting their aspirations.⁷
- Scarcity of Female Role Models: The absence of visible female role models in STEM creates a lack of inspiration and makes it difficult for girls to envision themselves in these fields. Seeing successful women in STEM can break down stereotypes and empower girls to pursue their interests.⁸
- Hostile Work Environment: STEM workplaces can be unwelcoming and hostile towards women, marked by experiences of sexism, harassment, and discrimination. These negative experiences can discourage women from entering or staying in STEM fields, perpetuating the gender gap.⁹
- Inequitable Access to Resources and Opportunities: Girls often have limited access to high-quality STEM programs, labs, technology, and extracurricular activities compared to boys. This disparity in resources creates unequal opportunities for development and can hinder girls' confidence and interest in STEM.¹⁰

⁷'Fast Facts: Early Barriers to Girls & Women in STEM' (AAUW : Empowering Women Since 18815 October 2020) <<https://www.aauw.org/resources/article/fast-facts-stem/>> accessed 13 December 2023

⁸Unesco Paris, Cracking the Code Girls' and Women's Education in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) (Paris Unesco 2017). 61

⁹Ibid. p.43

¹⁰'News & Insights' (AAUW : Empowering Women Since 1881, 12 September 2023) <<https://www.aauw.org/resources/news/media/>> accessed 13 December 2023

- Implicit Bias in STEM Education: Unconscious biases held by teachers and professors can lead to differential treatment and expectations for girls in STEM classrooms. This includes lower expectations, less encouragement, and even biased grading practices, disadvantaging girls and hindering their academic success.¹¹

Beyond Specific Barriers: Systemic Issues

While individual factors like stereotypes and lack of role models play a role, the underrepresentation of women in STEM also stems from systemic issues woven into educational and institutional practices. Let's delve into three crucial issues: standardized testing, the limited focus on critical thinking, and the lack of work-life balance support.

- Standardized Testing: Reliance on standardized tests, which often disadvantage girls in math and science, can lead to placement in lower-level STEM classes, limiting future opportunities and reinforcing negative stereotypes.¹²
- Limited Focus on Critical Thinking: STEM education often prioritizes rote memorization over critical thinking and problem-solving skills, essential for success in these fields. Girls, who tend to excel in these skills, are not adequately nurtured, further widening the achievement gap.¹³
- Lack of Work-Life Balance Support: Traditional STEM work cultures often demand long hours and inflexible schedules, making it challenging for women to balance

¹¹ Joseph R Cimpian, Taek H Kim and Zachary T McDermott, 'Understanding Persistent Gender Gaps in STEM' (2020) 368 Science 1317 <<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/368/6497/1317>>.

¹²'NCCWSL: AAUW's Student Leadership Conference' (AAUW : *Empowering Women Since 18816* December 2023) <<https://www.aauw.org/resources/events/nccwsl/>> accessed 13 December 2023

¹³Ibid

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their careers with family responsibilities. This lack of support discourages women from pursuing and thriving in STEM.¹⁴

WORKPLACE CHALLENGES AND THE GLASS CEILING IN STEM

Despite strides towards inclusivity, women in STEM fields remain tethered to a persistent obstacle: the glass ceiling. This invisible barrier, woven from a tapestry of challenges, restricts their ascent to leadership positions, leaving them underrepresented in the upper echelons of scientific and technological advancement. Unveiling and dismantling this barrier requires a nuanced understanding of the workplace factors that hinder their progress.¹⁵

One pervasive challenge is the persistent grip of gender stereotypes. STEM fields, often associated with masculinity and technical prowess, can be perceived as unwelcoming territories for women. This perception, fueled by unconscious bias and discriminatory practices, manifests in hiring, promotions, and performance evaluations, leaving women unfairly disadvantaged. The absence of visible female role models further exacerbates this issue. Lacking relatable examples of successful women in STEM leadership, aspiring women can feel discouraged and question their own potential, creating a self-fulfilling prophecy that perpetuates the underrepresentation cycle.¹⁶

Furthermore, the culture of many STEM workplaces can be hostile and alienating for women. Experiences of sexism, microaggressions, and even overt harassment can create a toxic environment that diminishes job satisfaction, hampers productivity, and ultimately drives women out of the field. This hostile climate not only impacts individual well-being

¹⁴Supra note.8 p.43

¹⁵ Smith-Walter, C. (2005). Gender stereotypes in contemporary science: Institutional effects and the reproduction of female underrepresentation. *Perspectives on Science*, 13(2), 233-261.

¹⁶ Moss-Racusin, C. A., Dovidio, J. F., Brescoll, V. L., & Byre, A. M. (2012). Science faculty's subtle gender bias: Does it matter for women's representation in science? *Psychological Science*, 23(1), 82-88.

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but also fuels the talent drain, depriving STEM of valuable diverse perspectives and innovative ideas.¹⁷

The challenge doesn't end there. Traditional STEM work cultures, notorious for demanding long hours and inflexible schedules, often clash with the demands of family life, disproportionately impacting women. Lack of access to flexible work arrangements and family-friendly policies can make it difficult for women to balance their careers with personal responsibilities, forcing them to choose between professional advancement and personal fulfillment.¹⁸

Finally, the lack of access to mentorship and sponsorship networks hinders women's progress in STEM. Mentors and sponsors provide crucial guidance, advocacy, and support, navigating the complex terrain of career advancement and leadership. However, women in STEM often face limited access to these valuable resources, leaving them to navigate the labyrinthine world of professional development alone.¹⁹

Addressing these challenges requires a multi-pronged approach. Implementing diversity and inclusion initiatives that actively dismantle unconscious bias and promote fair hiring and promotion practices is a crucial first step. Fostering mentorship and sponsorship programs specifically designed for women in STEM can provide the support and guidance necessary for their career advancement. Additionally, creating flexible work arrangements and family-friendly policies can help women balance their professional and personal lives, retaining valuable talent within the field.

¹⁷Supra note.8 p.57

¹⁸ Gottfried, A. E., & Feder, M. W. (2005). Gender and workplace flexibility: A review and analysis of the literature. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 26(1), 1-28.

¹⁹ Hewlett, S. A., & Hewlett, S. (2010). Mentor generation: How to guide and be guided. *Harvard Business Review*, 88(6), 72-80.

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By amplifying the success stories of women in STEM leadership, we can inspire future generations and challenge the prevailing stereotypes. Rigorous research, focused on understanding the specific challenges faced by women in STEM, can inform the development of evidence-based interventions that dismantle the glass ceiling, brick by brick.

Breaking free from the confines of the glass ceiling necessitates a collective effort. By acknowledging the workplace challenges, embracing inclusive practices, and celebrating the achievements of women in STEM, we can build a future where innovation and leadership are not hindered by gender, but fueled by diversity and inclusion. Only then can we truly unlock the full potential of STEM for all.

ROLE OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY, 2020 ON WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN STEM

The underrepresentation of women in STEM fields (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) remains a persistent global challenge. However, India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 presents a glimmer of hope for igniting the flames of female participation in these crucial domains. This transformative policy, with its emphasis on equity, inclusivity, and holistic learning, offers a potential roadmap for dismantling the barriers that have historically hindered women's progress in STEM.

One of the key strengths of NEP 2020 lies in its focus on dismantling gender stereotypes. By promoting gender-neutral language in textbooks and curricula, the policy aims to combat the harmful narratives that often associate STEM fields with masculinity. This shift in language and representation can empower young girls to see themselves as capable and deserving of pursuing careers in these traditionally male-dominated domains.²⁰

²⁰ National Education Policy 2020. (2020). Department of School Education and Literacy, Ministry of Education, Government of India. https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_E

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Furthermore, NEP 2020 emphasizes the importance of early childhood education (ECE) in fostering a love for STEM subjects. By providing access to quality ECE for all children, the policy aims to cultivate a foundation of curiosity and critical thinking skills, crucial for success in STEM fields. Additionally, the policy's focus on experiential learning and hands-on activities can further ignite girls' interest in STEM subjects, making them more likely to pursue them in higher education.

Beyond early education, NEP 2020 prioritizes providing girls with access to quality STEM education throughout their academic journey. This includes measures such as providing flexible learning pathways, eliminating rigid subject silos, and offering specialized support systems for girls in STEM fields. Additionally, the policy emphasizes the importance of mentorship and role models, encouraging universities and research institutions to create supportive networks where young women can connect with successful female scientists and engineers.²¹

However, it is crucial to acknowledge that simply establishing policies is not enough. To truly unlock the potential of NEP 2020 in boosting women's participation in STEM, effective implementation and ongoing monitoring are essential. This includes ensuring adequate funding for the implementation of the policy's provisions, addressing potential gender biases within the education system, and continuously evaluating the effectiveness of implemented initiatives²²

The National Education Policy 2020 presents a promising framework for fostering a more inclusive STEM landscape in India. By prioritizing gender equity, promoting early

²¹Ibid.

²² Singh, N. (2021). National Education Policy 2020: A critical analysis of the gender inclusivity dimension. *Gender in Education*, 33(1), 125-143. https://www.researchgate.net/72020_A_Critical_Analysis_of_Gender-inclusive_Perspectives

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childhood education, and providing girls with access to quality STEM education and support systems, the policy has the potential to ignite the flames of female participation in these crucial fields. However, the success of NEP 2020 will hinge on its effective implementation, rigorous monitoring, and a collective commitment to dismantling the systemic barriers that have historically held women back in STEM. Only then can India truly unlock the full potential of its female talent and thrive in the knowledge-driven future.

SUGGESTIONS

There are basically two aspects when it comes to the solving the problem of this whole dilemma of Navigating the Stem Landscape with Sociocultural Influences on Women's Stem Participation in India, which are: -

Research:

- Deepen understanding of regional variations: Investigate how sociocultural factors and their impact on girls' STEM aspirations differ across diverse regions and communities in India.
- Unravel intersectionality: Explore the complex interplay of gender with other social identities (caste, class, religion) and their combined influence on STEM access and participation.
- Evaluate existing interventions: Rigorously assess the effectiveness of existing initiatives aimed at increasing women's STEM participation, identifying areas for improvement and replication.
- Leverage technology: Investigate the potential of technology and digital platforms to provide accessible STEM education and mentorship opportunities for girls, particularly in remote areas.
- Longitudinal studies: Conduct longitudinal studies to track girls' STEM aspirations and career choices over time, understanding the long-term impact of interventions and sociocultural influences.

Policy:

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-
- Curriculum reform: Advocate for an overhaul of STEM education at all levels, incorporating gender-inclusive pedagogy, diverse role models, and hands-on learning opportunities.
 - Targeted scholarships and mentorship programs: Implement targeted scholarship and mentorship programs for girls from underprivileged backgrounds, addressing financial barriers and providing essential support.
 - Deconstruct gender stereotypes: Launch public awareness campaigns and educational programs to combat harmful gender stereotypes and biases associated with STEM fields.
 - Promote flexible work arrangements: Advocate for policies that promote flexible work arrangements and family-friendly workplaces in STEM fields, supporting women's work-life balance.
 - Invest in STEM infrastructure: Increase investment in research infrastructure and facilities in educational institutions to create a more welcoming and supportive environment for women in STEM.
 - Data collection and monitoring: Establish robust data collection and monitoring systems to track progress towards gender equity in STEM education and careers, informing future policy decisions.

CONCLUSION

In a world aspiring for equality, women's voices in decision-making aren't just threads - they're the vibrant fibers weaving progress. Their unique perspectives, born from lived experiences, enrich the tapestry of solutions, leading to inclusive, equitable outcomes.

Gender equality isn't just a moral imperative; it's a blueprint for a thriving society. Research paints a clear picture: more women at the table means improved economic growth, reduced poverty, and better governance - a family prospers when both parents contribute.

But the path to equal representation remains riddled with obstacles. Lack of resources, inadequate support networks, and ingrained biases are the knots women must untie. Yet, their contributions are indispensable. Their distinct perspectives, informed by personal

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experiences, add nuance to complex issues, weaving solutions that consider everyone.